

TiO₂-Graphite Supported Hybrid MIP Sensor for Sensitive Vitamin C Detection in Cosmetics

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Fig. S1. FE-SEM images of: (a) TiO₂ nanoparticles (b) AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G adduct (c) AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G after template removal, and (d) NI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G. (e) FTIR spectra of AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G before and after washing, NI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, and TiO₂@G. (f) UV-vis spectra of pure AA, TiO₂ nanoparticles, MIP before and after washing. EDX spectra of (g) the MIP adduct, and (h) the MIP after washing.

Fig. S2. Elemental distribution of (a) AA-MI-P(4-VP) $@TiO_2$ -G material before wash, (b) C atom, (c) N atom, (d) O atom, (e) Si atom, and (f) Ti atom.

Fig. S3. Elemental distribution of (a) AA-MI-P(4-VP) $@TiO_2$ -G material after wash, (b) C atom, (c) N atom, (d) O atom, (e) Si atom, and (f) Ti atom.

TABLE S1

BET OF SENSING MATERIALS

Properties	Leached MIP	Unleached MIP	NIP	TiO ₂ @G
Surface area (m ² /g)	57.560	40.224	25.992	37.264
Average pore radius (Å)	60.677	15.893	18.429	17.036
Total pore volume (cc/g)	0.253	0.190	0.138	0.242

Fig. S4. (a) BET nitrogen adsorption isotherms plot of leached and unleached AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, NI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, and TiO₂@G. BET pore volume and pore size distribution plots for: (b) leached AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, (c) unleached AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, (d) NI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G, and (e) TiO₂@G.

Fig. S5. Schematic of electrochemical oxidation of adsorbed AA at AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G matrix filled in capillary glass sensor.

Fig. S6. CVs of 200 μM AA in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7.0) at scan rate of 0.05 V.s⁻¹ using AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G sensor: (a) with TiO₂ synthesized at different temperatures, (b) with varying TiO₂ mixing ratios.

Fig. S7. CV responses of AA-MI-P(4-VP) $@TiO_2$ -G sensor in 200 μ M AA: (a) in different buffer electrolytes, (b) bar graph of peak current as a function of pH and (c) in PBS at different pH values (inset: plots of cathodic peak potential vs. pH [bottom] and anodic peak potential vs. pH [top]).

Fig. S8. Effect of scan rate on CV responses of 200 μ M AA in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7.0) using the AA-MI-P(4-VP) $@TiO_2$ -G sensor. Insets: plots of oxidation peak current vs. scan rate (top) and reduction peak current vs. scan rate (bottom).

Fig. S9. (a) Log-log plot of peak current vs. scan rate (inset: anodic peak current vs. square root of scan rate (top) and cathodic peak current vs. square root of scan rate (bottom)); (b) anodic peak potential vs. log of scan rate (inset: cathodic peak potential vs. log of scan rate).

Fig S10. DPV responses of the AA-MI-P(4-VP)@G sensor in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7.0) at a scan rate of 0.05 V.s⁻¹ for varying concentrations of AA: (a) current vs. potential plots for AA concentrations ranging from 10 to 100 μM (inset: 100-4000 μM), and (b) calibration plot of peak current vs. concentration from 10 to 4000 μM (inset: 10 to 100 μM).

Fig. S11. Bar plot showing the variation in DPV peak current response for 200 μM ascorbic acid in PBS (pH 7.0) in the presence of various interfering ions and structurally related compounds.

TABLE SII

INTERFERENCE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT SPECIES FOR THE DETERMINATION OF AA AT AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G SENSOR

Interferent	Interferent Concentration	Peak Current Response of 200 μM AA with Interferent (μA)	Relative Standard Deviation%
Na ⁺	2 mM	120.83	1.07
K ⁺	2 mM	117.32	1.85
NH ₄ ⁺	2 mM	119.16	0.31
NO ₃ ⁻	2 mM	119.11	0.36
Glucose	2 mM	117.57	1.65
Dopamine	2 mM	122.97	2.87

Uric Acid	2 mM	123.85	3.60
Citric Acid	2 mM	120.63	0.91
Gallic Acid	2 mM	117.46	1.74

Fig. S12. CV responses of AA-MI-P(4-VP)@ TiO₂-G sensor for 2mM of various interfering ions and structurally related compounds in PBS (pH 7.0)

TABLE SIII

DETECTION OF AA IN VARIOUS COSMETIC REAL SAMPLES AT AA-MI-P(4-VP)@TiO₂-G SENSOR USING STANDARD ADDITION TECHNIQUE

Sample	Added AA (μM)	Detected AA using spike current of DPV		Actual AA (μM)	Recovery ^a (%)	RSD (%) for n=3
		Average DPV Spike current (mA)	Detected AA using calibration equation (μM)			
V1	0	0.117	196.43	196.43	102.04	1.01
	50	0.146	247.45	246.43		
V2	0	0.147	249.46	249.46	104.97	3.46
	50	0.176	301.94	299.46		
V3	0	0.896	1594.91	1594.91	96.00	1.67
	50	0.923	1642.91	1644.91		
V4	0	0.065	102.43	102.43	96.18	2.31
	50	0.092	150.52	152.43		
V5	0	1.914	3420.12	3420.12	94.27	2.89
	50	1.939	3467.25	3470.12		

^a% of Recovery = [(Concentration found - Original concentration) / Added concentration] * 100

Fig. S13. DPV measurements of 200 μM AA in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7.0) using AA-MI-P(4-VP)@G sensor: (a) plot of current response against potential for six different sensors (S1-S6), (inset: repeatability test for ten measurements using the same sensor); (b) stability test for 30 days.